

Investigation of Acceleration at the Launch and Maximum Altitude of a Water Rocket

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1 Introduction

Water rockets are an accessible and visual model of jet propulsion, making them popular in educational physics experiments. The goal of our study was to investigate how the rocket's acceleration at launch depends on parameters such as initial pressure, water volume, and nozzle size. This article describes the experimental methodology, the theoretical flight model, and a comparative analysis of experimental data with calculated results.

2 Set up

Figure 1: Experimental setup

Figure 2: Automated plug

In the experiment, a sturdy bottle was used in which water was poured and pressure was pumped. A gray cap, consisting of two parts, was placed on the bottle. A stopper on a string prevented the cap from opening. When we pulled the string from a distance, the stopper was released, leaving the cap in place by friction. The pressure instantly overcomes the friction of the cap, causing it to open and allowing the water to flow out in a jet. This eliminated human error.

Another important detail was the guide rail. A component with a circular hole was attached to the rocket's body and placed onto a stand. This stand helped the rocket take off vertically without significant sideways deviations. Later, during the flight, the rocket naturally shifted along the X axis, but since we were studying acceleration at launch, this had no impact on the final research results.

3 Theoretical Modeling

3.1 Launch Condition

When pressure is pumped into the rocket using a pressure gauge, the plug is ejected due to the pressure difference inside and outside, creating a lift force opposite to the force and velocity of the ejected water jet.

For a successful launch, a certain condition must be met: the force of pressure on the plug and the weight of the water must overcome the friction of the cap to ensure its ejection.

$$\Delta P_{plug} S_{nozzle} + m_{water} g > F_{maxfriction} \quad (1)$$

Experimentally, this was achieved at $\Delta P \approx 0.7 \pm 0.2$ atm.

3.2 Rocket Motion Equations

We observe reactive motion according to Newton's third law: water, ejected from the bottle under pressure, creates an equal and opposite force that pushes the rocket upward.

As long as $m_{water}(t) > 0$, the motion of the rocket is described as follows:

$$M a_y = F_{thrust} - F_{drag} - Mg \quad (2)$$

Where: $M = m_{rocket} + m_{water}(t)$ is the current mass of the rocket, F_{thrust} is the thrust force generated by the expelled water, F_{drag} is the aerodynamic drag force, Mg is the gravitational force.

The thrust force is determined by the law of conservation of momentum:

$$F_{thrust} = \frac{dm_{water}}{dt} u \quad (3)$$

The drag force is calculated using the standard aerodynamic formula:

$$F_{drag} = C_x \frac{\rho v^2}{2} S \quad (4)$$

Where: C_x is the drag coefficient, ρ is the air density, v is the rocket velocity, S is the cross-sectional area of the rocket's top.

3.3 Pressure inside the rocket

We studied the formula for adiabatic pressure change in the literature. In this case, the process is adiabatic because the heat does not have time to escape. The adiabatic index, γ , was taken to be 1.4. A rocket was launched with a sensor, and the readings from the HW-611 barometer were plotted on a graph comparing theory and experiment.

$$P(t) = P_0 \left(\frac{V_{air,0}}{V_{air}(t)} \right)^\gamma \quad (5)$$

3.4 Water Jet Velocity

The velocity of the water jet can be determined using Bernoulli's equation. We make the following assumptions:

- The velocity of water inside the rocket is negligible (error is on the order of 2%).
- The hydrostatic pressure inside the rocket is small, on the order of 1000 Pa.
- The flow is laminar, and Bernoulli's equation is applicable.

$$u_{jet} = \sqrt{\frac{2\Delta P_{in}}{\rho}} \quad (6)$$

where: ΔP is the pressure difference outside and inside the rocket, ρ is the density of the fluid (water), u_{jet} is the velocity of the water jet at the nozzle.

Thus, the velocity of the water jet is determined by the internal pressure inside the rocket and the density of the water.

Figure 3

3.5 Air Resistance and Reynolds Number

To account for air resistance, we calculated the Reynolds number. The general formula for the Reynolds number is given by:

$$Re = \frac{u \cdot L \cdot \rho}{\mu} \quad (7)$$

where: u is the velocity of the fluid (water or air) relative to the object (rocket), L is the characteristic length (in our case, the size of the bottle), ρ is the density of the fluid (air), μ is the dynamic viscosity of the fluid (air).
Substituting values for our experiment into the formula:

$$Re = \frac{10^1 \cdot 10^{-1} \cdot 10^0}{20 \times 10^{-6}} = 10^5 \quad (8)$$

Thus, the Reynolds number for our experiment is approximately 10^5 .

Based on this Reynolds number, we determined the drag coefficient C_x . For $Re = 10^5$, the drag coefficient is $C_x = 0.84$.

3.6 Modeling with Python

We used all the formulas discussed above to model the rocket's flight. The modeling was implemented in Python, and the code is provided in the repository: [click here](#). The dependence of various parameters on time for the rocket was simulated under the conditions of a pressure of 4.5 atmospheres and a water volume of 100 mL.

Below are the plots that show the results of the simulation:

Figure 4: The graph of rocket height as a function of time.

Figure 5: The graph of rocket velocity as a function of time. We observe that the rocket's speed increases very quickly, taking about 0.1 seconds, after which it gradually slows down.

Figure 6: The graph of rocket acceleration as a function of time. We can see a sharp peak in acceleration at the beginning of the flight, and as the water runs out, the rocket's acceleration suddenly drops.

Figure 7: The graph of pressure as a function of time. It goes down fast as water ends.

3.7 Theory and Experiment Comparison

3.7.1 Height vs. Time Comparison

The graph below shows the experimental data, which were obtained from the sensors during the launch. The graph shows good agreement with the theory throughout the entire motion, except at the end. This discrepancy arises because our theoretical model describes the rocket's motion while there is still water inside. However, at the end of the motion, no water remains in the bottle, and the remaining gas escapes. As a result, the bottle (rocket body) starts spinning, its drag force changes, and its trajectory becomes unpredictable.

3.7.2 Acceleration vs. Time Comparison

The accelerometer was unable to measure the required values as it maxed out. To address this, we analyzed a simulation graph of maximum acceleration as a function of the water volume in the rocket. Based on this analysis,

Figure 8: Comparison of height vs. time: Theory vs. Experiment

we determined that using 1 liter of water would be optimal for comparing the experiment with the theory. With this volume, the acceleration remains within a measurable range, ensuring accurate data collection.

Figure 9: Graph of maximum acceleration as a function of water volume

Comparing experiment with theory:

$$a_{max\ exp} = (192 \pm 10) \text{ m/s}^2$$

$$a_{max\ theory} = 200 \text{ m/s}^2$$

The experiment shows good agreement with the theory.

4 Experiments

In this section, we analyze the dependence of the rocket's maximum height on various parameters. Specifically, we vary the water volume, the nozzle diameter (our nozzle caps were 3D-printed, allowing us to modify their parameters), and the internal pressure of the rocket. Below are graphs where the theoretical curves represent an approximation of theoretical points obtained by solving the differential equations derived from our theoretical model.

Figure 10: Dependence of maximum height on water volume

Figure 11: Dependence of maximum height on nozzle diameter

Figure 12: Dependence of maximum height on internal pressure

Now, we analyze the behavior of acceleration graphs. We calculate the average acceleration using the equation:

$$a = \frac{v^2 - v_0^2}{2S} \quad (9)$$

We compute this value for the first seconds of flight and analyze the resulting trends.

Figure 13: Dependence of average acceleration on water volume

Figure 14: Dependence of average acceleration on nozzle diameter

Figure 15: Dependence of average acceleration on internal pressure

4.1 Analysis of the Graphs

The graphs reveal that there are optimal values for the water volume. This is because water simultaneously provides thrust by forming a jet that propels the rocket upwards while also adding weight, which counteracts the thrust.

In the case of the nozzle diameter, we observe that the height has a minimum value. This is because with a small nozzle the jet velocity is high, while as the diameter increases, the height decreases because the water is expelled too quickly. However, acceleration continuously increases, as it is not directly dependent on height. Acceleration will be greater with higher ejection velocity, resulting in stronger thrust, but only for a short duration. In addition, it is important to consider the existence of limits. If the nozzle diameter is equivalent to the rocket body size, special edge cases may occur.

For internal pressure, there is an upper limit: excessive pressure can rupture the bottle. In our experiments, at 7 atmospheres, the attached components of the setup started to break down, indicating a structural limit for safe operation.

5 Conclusion

The experimental study of water rockets provided valuable insights into the factors affecting their performance. The main conclusions are as follows:

- The rocket's motion is propelled by the ejection of water in the opposite direction, causing the rocket to move forward according to Newton's third law. The flow of water is described using Bernoulli's law, which relates pressure and velocity of the fluid at different points. Air resistance is also taken into account.
- The rocket's acceleration is mainly affected by internal pressure, water volume, and nozzle diameter. There is an optimal water volume (around 30-40% of the volume of the rocket) that maximizes thrust, with diminishing returns as volume increases.
- The nozzle diameter significantly affects both height and acceleration. Smaller diameters increase jet velocity, while larger ones cause faster water expulsion, reducing height.
- Internal pressure must be controlled to avoid structural failure. Pressures above 7 atmospheres caused setup failures, indicating a safe operational limit.
- The experimental results are in good agreement with the theoretical predictions, with the maximum acceleration measured experimentally being close to the theoretical value.

In future studies, further investigation could explore the impact of different rocket designs, such as varying the shape of the bottle or the addition of fins, to improve stability and performance.

6 References

References

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